

Kinetics and Mechanisms of Oxidation of Ascorbic Acid by Cobalt(III) Complexes*

C. CHATTERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Mumbai-400 076

Electron transfer plays a central role in many physical, chemical and biological processes¹. Biological processes like photosynthesis and respiration involve a series of reactions which are effectively controlled by electron transfer. In chemical reactions, electron transfer occurs on a time scale from femto seconds to seconds, and at distances less than 0.1 nm to about 1.0 nm. Technologically challenging processes like solar energy conversion, non-linear optics, information storage devices, molecular recognition etc. are dependent on electron transfer. The great importance of electron transfer reactions, fueled interest in theoretical developments right from the early stages of research in this field. Since then, there has been a strong interplay between theory and experiments related to outer-sphere electron transfer reactions. Experimental work of Taube and theoretical efforts of Marcus are the high points of early research in the area of electron transfer. Hush, Libby, Dogonadze and Levich contributed much to develop theories and experiments². To date, great deal has been learned about electron transfer reactions, but some questions in both theoretical as well as experimental area are yet to be answered. Therefore, understanding the factors which determine the electron transfer rate are of great importance. Although the oxidation and reduction of reactants is a simple process, the pathways followed by reaction are complex. In 1950, two major pathways, viz. Outer-sphere and Inner-sphere were recognised. Outer-sphere reactions are those in which the electron transfer occurs because of electronic coupling between two reaction centres through space while, inner-sphere processes are those in which electronic interactions is promoted by chemical bond formation. The outer-sphere reaction is further classified into 'adiabatic' and 'non-adiabatic' reactions. In adiabatic or 'strong overlap' case, the electronic interaction between reactants is strong, as it occurs over a shorter distance, and electronic transmission coefficient is approximately equal to one. While, in non-adiabatic or 'weak overlap' case, there is weak interaction of orbitals which leads to transmission coefficient being less than unity.

Transition metal complexes have been extensively used for studying electron transfer reactions. Amongst them octahedral cobalt(III) complexes being substitutionally inert are ideal for theoretical and experimental studies. The kinetics of reduction of cobalt(III) complexes is thus free

from complications arising due to reversible electron transfer, aquation, substitution and isomerisation reactions. Cobalt(III) complexes are in general low-spin, while cobalt(II) complexes in absence of very strong field ligands, show high-spin behaviour. Thus, a change in spin multiplicity involved makes greater contribution to study their cross as well as self-exchange reactions³. Most of the studies related to redox reactions of cobalt, pertain to reduction of cobalt(III) complexes by different inorganic reductants, such as Cr^{II}, V^{II}, Fe^{II}, Eu^{II}, Mo^{IV} etc., in the form of their aqua complexes as well as complexes of other ligands. In contrast, reactions involving non-metallic inorganic or organic reductants have been scarcely reported. Some of the organic reductants used for such studies have been *ortho*- and *para*-dihydroxybenzene, ascorbic acid etc.⁴. Oxidation of organic compounds by transition metal complexes has been intensively investigated in the light of not only industrial benefits but also modelling metalloenzymatic systems for elucidation of their functions and mechanisms, in which radical intermediates are often involved. The oxidation processes catalysed by transition metal complexes include activation of substrates and/or reactants and often involve electron transfer reactions from substrates to metal centres⁵.

L-Ascorbic acid :

L-Ascorbic acid, known as vitamin C, is found naturally in a wide variety of plants and animals. Its main biochemical role is as a redox reagent⁶. The role of vitamin C in the cure of scurvy is a well studied and documented fact. Besides, ascorbic acid is finding increasing applications in multicomponent redox system for photolysis of water⁷. Therefore, the knowledge of parameters which control the rate of ascorbate reactions is highly desirable. The structure of *L*-ascorbic acid as determined in solid state by *X*-ray crystallography is shown in Fig. 1. A notable feature of this structure is the ene-diol arrangement because of which, 3-hydroxyl group is ionised first. In an excellent resume of the complex redox behaviour of *L*-ascorbic acid, Creutz⁸ pointed out that the oxidation-reduction reactions involving ascorbic acid are complicated due to intervening simultaneous proton transfer reactions. In aqueous medium it behaves as a diprotic acid and a two-electron reducing agent. It is a weak acid, but the radical produced during redox reactions, which is comparatively stable, is a strong acid.

*Prof. P. K. Bose Memorial Lecture (1993) delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on 27 December, 1996 at Coimbatore.

Fig. 1

Fig. 1 depicts structures of various redox products of ascorbic acid, while Fig. 2 represents different species formed in the oxidation-reduction reactions of ascorbic acid along with acid dissociation constants and redox potentials⁸. In redox reactions involving ascorbic acid as a coreactant, several possibilities are indicated by a variety of species available from it during oxidation-reduction reactions. A vast majority of the reactions of transition metal ions with ascorbic acid have been investigated in the range of pH 2–8, where H₂A and HA⁻ are predominant reaction species. One-electron oxidation of ascorbic acid produces either

Fig. 2. Redox potentials and acidity constants for electron exchange of ascorbic acid and related species; all data at 25° and ionic strength 0.1 M

HA[·] or A⁻, while two-electron oxidation leads to dehydroascorbic acid, A (Fig. 1). The large difference in reactivity between protonated and dissociated forms of ascorbic acid have been rationalised in terms of the redox potentials and self-exchange rate constants. In most cases, the formation of ascorbate radical is proposed in the rate-limiting step and the ultimate product is assumed to be dehydroascorbic acid.

Redox reactions of substitutionally inert octahedral cobalt(III) complexes provide opportunity for study of both outer- and inner-sphere reactions. Rickman *et al.*⁹ studied reduction of hexa-aquacobalt(III) ion by L-ascorbic acid in strongly acidic medium ([H⁺] from 0.6 to 3.0 mol dm⁻³). Similar to all other reductions involving aqua complexes cobalt(III) species, this reaction shows first order dependence both in Co^{III} as well as the reductant, and the second order rate constant follows an empirical relationship, $k_{\text{obs}} = a + (b/[\text{H}^+])$. Inverse hydrogen ion concentration dependence is explained by participation of aquahydroxocobalt(III) species in the reaction. Even at fairly high [H⁺], the reaction has to be followed using stopped flow technique. On comparing kinetic data with reactions of other reductants, the possibility of chelation by ascorbic acid before electron transfer is ruled out. The redox reaction has been suggested to proceed by outer-sphere mechanism. In comparison, oxidation of L-ascorbic acid by tris-oxalatocobaltate(III) is much slower in range of pH 3.2 to 4.7 at an ionic strength of 1.0 mol dm⁻³.¹⁰ Rate of reaction shows an inverse hydrogen ion concentration, which is explained by protonation-deprotonation equilibrium involving ascorbic acid. Involvement of both H₂A and HA⁻ has been suggested in the oxidation reaction. An outer-sphere mechanism is proposed for the reaction. Using Marcus cross relation, redox potentials for H₂A^{·+}/H₂A and HA[·]/HA⁻ couples have been estimated. Martinez *et al.*¹¹ extended these investigations in weakly basic medium (pH 8–10), where ascorbate dianion (A²⁻) is suggested to be the only reactive species. From these studies, the order of reactivity for reduction of [Co(ox)₃]³⁻ by various ascorbic acid species has been found to be : A²⁻ > HA⁻ > H₂A. Comparison of activation parameters revealed, significant enhancement in rates is accompanied by a decrease in enthalpy of activation to the tune of 20 kJ mol⁻¹ and very little change in the entropy of activation. Thus, the rate of oxidation of ascorbic acid by [Co(ox)₃]³⁻ seems to be controlled by an activation enthalpy barrier for electron transfer.

The reaction of pentaamminechlorocobalt(III) ion with ascorbic acid has been studied in the pH range 0.8–2.0¹². An outer-sphere mechanism is proposed with ascorbic acid radical as the first product which then rapidly reduces a further mole of the complex.

Tsukahara and Yamamoto¹³ investigated the oxidation of ascorbic acid by a series of cobalt(III) complexes containing α-diimine ligands such as [Co(bipy)₃]³⁺ and [Co(en)(phen)₂]³⁺ in weakly acidic medium (pH 3.6–5.04).

Scheme 1

The mechanism (Scheme 1) leads to a rate law,

$$1/2[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]/dt = k[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}] [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_0$$

where the second order rate constant k is given by

$$k = (k_0 + k_1K_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]^2)/\alpha(\text{H})$$

and $\alpha(\text{H}) = 1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]^{-1} + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]^{-2}$

The authors pointed out that, $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_3]^{3+}$, and $[\text{Co}(\text{phen})_3]^{3+}$ are reduced by both HA^- and A^{2-} , while $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{phen})_2]^{3+}$ is reduced only by A^{2-} . In case of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{phen})]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ even ascorbate anion failed to react. This difference in reactivity can be attributed to the differences in redox potentials of the complex studied. In cases where both HA^- and A^{2-} are reactive, A^{2-} reacts about 10^6 times faster than HA^- .

The kinetics of outer-sphere oxidation of ascorbic acid by bis(terpyridine)cobalt(III) have been reported¹⁴ over a wide range of hydrogen ion concentration (pH 5–11.7). The rate of reaction showed an inverse dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ and ascorbate dianion (A^{2-}) is the most active reductant in comparison to other species.

The kinetics of reduction of cobalt(III) complexes containing macrocyclic- N_4 type ligands (Fig. 3) by L-ascorbic acid have been studied over the pH range 1.64–3.47. As-

 Fig 3. Structure of tetraazamacrocycles (N_4)

corbate monoanion (HA^-) is found to reduce both $\text{Co}(\text{N}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{3+}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{N}_4)(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ complexes of ligand I, II and III, while only aquahydroxo complex of ligand IV is reducible. The complexes of ligands I, II and III exhibit usual behaviour of rate being first order in complex and reductant, and inverse variation of k_{obs} with hydrogen ion concentration. In contrast, the complex of ligand IV reacts in a biphasic manner, which is attributed to the oxidation of reduced complex by oxygen. The diqua complexes are suggested to proceed by an outer-sphere electron transfer mechanism while the reactions of aqua hydroxo complexes to proceed via an OH-bridged mechanism. The lack of saturation of macrocyclic ligands facilitate the electron transfer reaction between cobalt(III) and ascorbic acid.

In an interesting study, kinetics and mechanism of ascorbic acid oxidation by 12-tungstocobaltate(III), $[\text{Co}(\text{III})\text{-O}_4\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{36}]^{6-}$ have been investigated in acidic media¹⁵. The $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ couple undergoes reversible reduction. As the complex is substitutionally inert electron transfer is believed to proceed by an outer-sphere mechanism. Ascorbate monoanion, HA^- is suggested to be the reactive species as the reaction is highly pH-dependent even at high hydrogen ion concentrations (0.04–1.00 mol dm^{-3}). Recently, Martinez *et al.*¹⁶ reported the oxidation of ascorbic acid by $\text{cis-}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{OH}_2)_2]^{3+}$ ion in weakly acidic media (pH 2.8–3.5). The kinetic data are interpreted in terms of rate-determining oxidation of the deprotonated ascorbate monoanion by an outer-sphere pathway. The ion-pair formation theory of Fuoss and the Marcus-Sutin cross relationship for electron transfer were applied to estimate electron transfer rate constant and self-exchange rate constant for the $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{OH}_2)_2^{2+/3+}$ couple.

Among the various types of multidentate ligands, aminopolycarboxylic acids have drawn special attention owing to their application in both applied and fundamental research. The high complexing ability of these ligands have been utilised to remove toxic metal ions from biological systems. Metal chelates are also employed as probes in biophysical experiments¹⁷. Donor groups of aminopolycarboxylic acids are similar to amino acid residues¹⁸ and hence, studies involving these ligands are of considerable physiological significance. The difference in number of carboxylato groups and their backbone offers variation in structural as well as electronic properties of the complexes like hydrophobicity, reduction potential etc. Aminopolycarboxylato complexes thus have attracted considerable attention in recent years for elucidating mechanisms of electron transfer reactions¹⁹. Different aminopolycarboxylic acids have been advantageously utilised in our laboratory to vary charge on the complex and alter their structural and their electronic properties. Of the aminopolycarboxylic acids used, ethylene diamine- N,N' -diacetic acid (edda) is a linear, tetradentate ligand while, nitrilotriacetic acid (nta) and N -(*o*-carboxyphenyl)iminodiacetic acid (cpida) are tripodal, tetradentate type. The cpida ligand differs from nta by virtue of presence of a

bulky aromatic ring along with an electron-withdrawing group (COOH). Diamine ligands like 1,2-diaminoethane (en) and 1,3-diaminopropane (tn) have been used to occupy the remaining two vacant sites in octahedral cobalt(III) complexes resulting in mixed ligand compounds. Different stabilities of five- and six-membered chelate rings formed by en and tn ligands respectively have further contributed to the variation in reactivities of the complexes. Kinetics of oxidation of L-ascorbic acid by aminopolycarboxylato-cobalt(III) complexes have been studied as a function of pH, temperature, ionic strength and ascorbic acid concentration. The reaction is first order with respect to both the complex and ascorbic acid. The oxidation reaction has been studied in the pH range 8.0–10.0 and whose rate is strongly dependent on the pH of the medium, suggesting ascorbate dianion as the most active reductant rather than ascorbate monoanion. Based on the kinetic data the following mechanism is proposed,

The ionic strength (μ) dependence of the rate and the magnitude of the slope of the linear plot of $\log k$ versus $\mu^{1/2}$ lend additional support in favour of the proposed scheme. As the complexes used are substitutionally inert, an outer-sphere mechanism has been suggested for the reaction. The order of reactivity of the complexes towards ascorbic acid oxidation is, $[\text{Co}(\text{nta})(\text{tn})] > [\text{Co}(\text{nta})(\text{en})] > [\text{Co}(\text{cpida})(\text{tn})] > [\text{Co}(\text{cpida})(\text{tn})] > [\text{Co}(\text{cpida})(\text{en})]^+ > [\text{Co}(\text{edda})(\text{tn})]^+ > [\text{Co}(\text{edda})(\text{en})]^+$. Higher reactivity of tn complexes reflects the relaxation of strain in the chelate ring on reduction, while lower reactivity of cpida complexes can be attributed to the presence of a bulky aromatic ring present in the backbone of cpida ligand which hinders metal-ligand bond extension as compared to that of nta complexes²⁰. Oxidation of ascorbic acid by *trans*(N)-[Co(NTA)(gly)]⁻, *trans*(N)-[Co(NTA)(pic)]⁻, [Co(NTA)(ox)]²⁻, [Co(edda)(bipy)]⁺ and [Co(edda)(phen)]⁺ complexes has also been investigated in the author's laboratory. The pH range studied is 7.5 < pH < 10.0 for the nta complexes and 4.0 < pH < 6.0 for the edda complexes. Pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) is observed to increase rapidly with increase in pH of the medium, suggesting participation of ascorbate monoanion (HA⁻) and ascorbate dianion (A²⁻) in the rate-determining step. Based on the kinetic results the following mechanistic scheme is suggested :

In accordance with the proposed mechanistic scheme, the rate for the nta complexes can be expressed as

$$-d[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]/dt = 2[\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{tot}}\{k_1K_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2K_1K_2/(K_1K_2 + [\text{H}^+]^2)\}[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}].$$

Under the experimental pH range, $[\text{H}^+]^2$ is negligible and $K_1K_2 \ll K_1[\text{H}^+]$. Hence, the above equation reduces to

$$k_{\text{obs}} = 2 [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{tot}}\{k_1 + k_2K_2/[\text{H}^+]\}$$

The plot of k_{obs} versus pH gives a quadratic curve indicating the presence of a reactive species whose concentration is strongly dependent on pH of the medium. A plot of k_{obs} versus inverse of hydrogen ion concentration at constant ascorbic acid concentration gives a straight-line with an intercept, further validates the proposed mechanism. While in the case of edda complex, according to the suggested mechanistic scheme, the plot of $k/[\text{H}^+] \{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+]^{-1}\}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ should be linear. Actually such plots have been observed and linearity of the plots supports the mechanism proposed. Comparison of second order rate constants reveals that A²⁻ species is atleast 10³ times more reactive than HA⁻ in case of all the complexes used for the study. The electron transfer reaction appears to be controlled by the enthalpy of activation barrier rather than entropy of activation. As the complexes are substitutionally inert, an outer-sphere mechanism has been suggested for the reaction. Reduction potentials for the metal complexes under investigation were calculated using activation parameters and Marcus equation²¹ in the form of

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_{12}^\ddagger &= W_{12} + \lambda (1 + \Delta G_{12}^\ddagger/\lambda)^2/4 \\ k_{12} &= Z \exp (-\Delta G_{12}^\ddagger/RT) \\ \lambda &= 2(\Delta G_{11}^\ddagger - W_{11} + \Delta G_{22}^\ddagger - W_{22}) \\ W_{ij} &= Z_i Z_j e^2 N_A / 4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon\sigma(1 + \alpha\sigma) \end{aligned}$$

The calculated values fall in the same range as that of other cobalt(III) aminopolycarboxylato complexes²². The mixed ligand Co^{III}nta complexes follow the trend in the reactivity as : [Co(NTA)(gly)]⁻ < [Co(NTA)(ox)]²⁻ < [Co(NTA)(pic)]⁻, while in the case of edda complexes [Co(edda)(phen)]⁺ reacts faster than [Co(edda)(bipy)]⁺ (Ref. 23). The reactivity pattern has been rationalised in terms of the nature of the ligands. As cobalt(III) prefers N-donor atoms as coordinated ligands, N–O donor glycinate ligand stabilises the cobalt(III) complex more than the O–O donor oxalato ligand. Although the picolinato ligand possesses similar N–O chelation like glycinate, it reacts at a faster rate than glycinate or oxalato complexes. The higher reactivity of the picolinato complex can be ascribed to its π -acceptor property which in turn facilitates the electron transfer from a π -donor ascorbate anion. Extended Hückel π MO calculations²⁴ suggest that the lowest π^* orbital energy for phenanthroline ligand is about 8 kJ mol⁻¹ higher than that

of bipyridyl ligand, which accounts for higher reactivity of [Co(edda)(phen)]⁺ complex ion.

References

1. K. V. MIKKELSON and M. A. RATNAR, *Chem. Rev.*, 1987, **87**, 113.
2. J. J. ZUKERMAN, "Inorganic Reaction and Methods", VCH, Florida, 1986, Vol. 15.
3. H. DONIE and T. W. SWADDLE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 1858.
4. R. D. CANNON, "Electron Transfer Reactions", Butterworths, London, 1980; "Mechanisms of Inorganic and Organometallic Reactions", ed. M. V. TWIGG, 1983-1987, Vols. 1-5.
5. T. КОЛМА, J. TSUCHIYA, S. NAKASHINA, H. OHYA-NISHIGUCHI, S. YANO and M. HIDAI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 2333.
6. N. H. WILLIAMS and J. K. YANDELL, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1982, **35**, 1133.
7. G. M. BROWN, B. S. BRUNSCHWIG, C. CREUTZ, J. F. ENDICOTT and N. SUTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 1298.
8. C. CREUTZ, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 4449.
9. R. A. RICKMAN, R. L. SORENSEN, K. D. WATKINS and G. DAVIES, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 1570.
10. M. KIMURA, Y. YAMAMOTO and S. YANABE, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1982, 423.
11. P. MARTINEZ, J. ZULUAGA, J. KRAFT and R. VAN ELDIK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **146**, 9.
12. P. MARTINEZ, A. F. RODRIGUEZ and J. ZULUAGA, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1989, **270**, 491.
13. K. TSUKAHARA and Y. YAMAMOTO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1981, **54**, 2642.
14. K. TSUKAHARA, T. IZUMITANI and Y. YAMAMOTO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1982, **55**, 130.
15. Z. AMIAD, J. C. BRODVITCH and A. MCAULEY, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1981, **55**, 3581.
16. P. MARTINEZ, J. ZULUAGA, P. NOHEDA and R. VAN ELDIK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1992, **195**, 249.
17. G. F. MEARS and T. G. WENSEL, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1984, **17**, 202.
18. D. R. RADANOVIC, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1984, **54**, 159.
19. H. OGINO and M. SHIMURA in "Advances in Inorganic and Bioinorganic Mechanisms", ed. A. G. SYKES, Academic, London, 1986, Vol. 4, p. 107.
20. S. BHONDRE, Ph.D. Thesis, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, 1993.
21. R. A. MARCUS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 891.
22. R. A. RADER and D. R. McMILLAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 545.
23. R. D. MAKOTE, Ph.D. Thesis, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, 1996.
24. G. N. LAMAR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 9055.